

INDEPENDENT INTERNATIONAL COMMISSION ON DECOMMISSIONING

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STATEMENT

6 January 2009

“The IICD confirms that, having started the decommissioning process with the Ulster Defence Association last June, we have now conducted a major act of decommissioning in which arms, ammunition, explosives and explosive devices belonging to the Ulster Defence Association have been destroyed within the terms of our mandate.

The leadership of the Ulster Defence Association has informed us that these armaments constitute the totality of those under their control.

The IICD reminds paramilitary organizations which may still have arms in their possession that we have until the 9th of February this year to complete our mandate and we urge them to contact us soon to that effect.”

End of statement